

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IS THE BASIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION.

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Annotation: This article contains information about the correct use of pedagogical and innovative technologies in the educational process, which today causes widespread discussion, and its role in teaching students. Trainings enable young people to express their attitude to important life achievements and problems, freely express their opinions and justify their point of view.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hozirgi kunda keng muhokamalarga sabab bo'layotgan ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida pedagogik hamda innovatsion texnologiyalarning to'g'ri qo'llanilishi hamda buning talabalarning bilim olishlarida tutgan o'rni haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Pedagogik texnologiya asosida o'tkazilgan mashg'ulotlar yoshlarning muhim hayotiy yutuq va muammolarga o'z munosabatlarini bildirishlari o'z fikrlarini erkin bayon etishlari va o'z nuqtai nazarlarini asoslashga imkoniyat yaratadi.

Аннотация: В данной статье содержится информация о правильном использовании педагогических и инновационных технологий в образовательном процессе, вызывающем сегодня широкие дискуссии, и его роли в обучении студентов. Тренинги дают возможность молодежи выразить свое отношение к важным жизненным достижениям и проблемы, свободно выражать свое мнение и обосновывать свою точку зрения.

Key words: Pedagogical technologies, integrated lessons, educational process, innovative technologies, competency-based approaches.

Kalit so'z: Pedagogik texnologiya, integrallashgan darslar, ta'lim jarayoni, innovatsion texnologiyalar, kompetensiyaviy yondashuvlar

Ключевые слова: Педагогические технологии, интегрированные уроки, образовательный процесс, инновационные технологии, компетентностные подходы.

2020 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, he stated that the program idea "From National Revival to National Uplift" is a very honorable task of educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, developing initiative, purposefulness, and moral quality in them. Today, an institutional system for the development of the national idea has been formed in Uzbekistan (the Nobel laureate Douglas North is recognized as the father of this direction), increasing its effectiveness requires the teaching of social and human sciences at school, including in higher education institutions depends on how it is taught. It is very important to pay attention to the area in which specialists in teaching these subjects are trained in higher education institutions. In today's globalizing world, the main advantage of highly developed countries is

determined by the state of the education system, the availability of opportunities for personal development. The factors that ensure stable economic growth of the state today and in the future are directly related to the development of the education sector. The role of primary education in human development is incomparable. In particular, in the modern system of primary education, integrated lessons and competence-based approaches determine the perspective of primary education.

In modern primary education, learning activities are carried out in accordance with the age, physiological characteristics and thinking of the student. The need to eliminate the existing discrepancy between the current level of development of science, technology and technology and the process of improving the professional training of future teachers is becoming increasingly relevant due to the insufficient introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies into the higher education system. Modern innovations in science and technology require their rapid inclusion in the content of educational programs and textbooks, thereby creating the basis for the formation of modern knowledge of students. The introduction of modern teaching technologies and various methodological approaches, in turn, creates favorable conditions for the relatively easy and strong formation of many fundamental concepts among students.

2020 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev Appeal to the Oliy Majlis of January 24.

We must not forget that the foundation of our future is created in the field of knowledge, in other words, the future of our people depends on the education and upbringing of our children today. To do this, every parent, teacher and coach must first of all see a person in the personality of each child. Based on this simple requirement, the education in our children of perfect people, with the skills of independent and broad thinking, living consciously, should be the main goal and task of the field of education. Today it is no secret to anyone that the use of innovative technologies in the education of the younger generation guarantees a higher level of results than traditional classes. This is a fact of life, because the need for it is also felt in the primary education of the general education school. After all, trainings conducted on the basis of innovative technologies satisfy the desire of young people to express their attitude to important life achievements and problems, create an opportunity for them to think and justify their point of view. Especially at present, interest and attention to improving the effectiveness of education through the widespread use of interactive methods (innovative pedagogy and technology) in the educational process is growing day by day. Classes with the use of modern technologies are aimed at independent study and analysis of the knowledge gained by students and summing up. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the formation and education of students and groups, and also plays the role of a manager and mentor. The correct use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process leads to the fact that the teacher acts as the main organizer or consultant in this process. This requires students to be more independent, creative and willpower. Trainings conducted on the basis of pedagogical technology enable young people to express their attitude to important life achievements and problems, freely express their opinion and justify their point of view. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and activities of the teacher and student, and interactive methods are mainly used in their implementation.

When using modern pedagogical technologies in the lessons:

- to democratize the educational process - to give students the right to freely express their opinions, to form their cognitive activity, to create a benevolent and comfortable socio-psychological environment based on mutual solidarity;

- we believe that it is necessary to use various methods and means in lectures, seminars, traditional and test classes.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in connection with the development of pedagogical technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, it becomes obvious that the imperative of the time for everyone is to strengthen their professional training and skills. At the same time, based on the generalization of the experience of the advanced countries of the world, they form a new social culture among young people, helping them to correctly determine their path, based on the principles of development, without repeating the mistakes of the past, drawing the necessary lessons from them, the main threats to the development and future of the nation, it will be possible to foresee the factors and to eliminate them in time, to ensure peaceful coexistence with the peoples of the world. President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev speaks about this: "...We all understand very well that education is the most important priority issue of any country and society, which is being addressed not only today, but also tomorrow. Therefore, in our country, this issue is given great attention at the state level.

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